

PROFESSIONAL ETHICS OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS OFFICERS

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Annotation: The purpose of this article is to identify ethical principles and rules of professional activity of employees of Internal Affairs which are guided by codes of ethics. The article proves the importance of professional ethics in performance of the duties especially to maintain professional integrity. It is essential to know the rules of ethics to fulfill their duties and ensure high standards of conduct.

Key words: professional ethics, morality, manner, society, legal order, behavioral standards
Today, all socio-economic, political-legal and spiritual-cultural changes taking place in the life of our free Motherland, on the one hand, create objective conditions for the change and development of a person, and on the other hand, creates a great need for physically healthy, morally pure, spiritually mature people with comprehensive and deep knowledge for the society that is being built.

Therefore, it is difficult to imagine during the process of establishing a legal democratic state in our country without patriotic, faith-believing, kind-hearted people who love their profession and possess high culture.

Solving the responsible issue of educating such creators and owners of our great future, first of all, law enforcement agencies are entrusted with a number of tasks related to strengthening the legal order, protecting the rights and legitimate interests of citizens, fighting against crime, and improving the educational work in the direction of improving the legal culture of the people; secondly, it is necessary to regularly fill its ranks with politically mature, morally pure, loyal to the profession, with the idea of justice in mind, highly qualified specialists who are not afraid of difficulties, and clean it from employees who have suffered professional downturn unable to cope with the hardships of service.

Also, the great orator of the East, Husayn Vaiz Koshifi, in his book entitled "Futuvvatnomayi sultaniy yohud javonmardlik tarikati" elaborates on the problems of professional ethics and professional manners. In particular, the fourteenth, fifteenth and sixteenth chapters of the fifth chapter of the book are devoted to the etiquette of various professions. For example, the fourteenth chapter is called "About the businessman and commercial etiquette and includes the rules of etiquette for the owner of the profession as well as commercial people". Koshifi writes: "You should know that there are short rules of etiquette that apply equally to all professions, and there are specific etiquettes for each profession. If they ask how many there are summaries of essential etiquette for all professions, say eight: first, you should maintain professional integrity from illegitimacy and dubious wealth. Secondly, you should engage in profession only for the necessity of living, and should not use your profession to accumulate wealth. Thirdly, you should know that the profession is the reason for gaining reputation and making a good name. Fourthly, do not

communicate with people who profit from such haram actions (officials, bribers, robbers, thieves, gamblers, dishonest shopkeepers)...¹

Morality it is one of the beginnings of the perfection of humanity. Through it, every person realizes his place in society, through it determines the meaning of his life. Therefore, since ancient times, the issue of ethics has been the center of attention of sages, public figures and statesmen, as well as the state. Because no country can achieve its goals without establishing ethical relations and forming a culture of professional ethics. Therefore, it is consider to be as one of the urgent issues facing our country today.

Ethics and its definition. It is true that in democratic societies founded on the principles of the rule of law, the police carry out their traditional duties, which include preventing, detecting, and combating crime, maintaining public order, ensuring observance of the law and public order and protection the rights of citizens , and offering assistance and services to the populace.

The word ethics is derived from the Greek ethikos, meaning "character."² Ethics is the moral behavior of an individual or group in its environment. This definition may be used to individuals or group in community; it is essential individual or group to be in law enforcement. According to Delattre (1996) public safety officials must have a higher moral standart than the general public. There is no difference between police ethics and other profession's ethics. However, for those in law enforcement, the behavioral standards and the implications of failure are more visible and problematic. Therefore, finding methods and practices to guarantee particular conduct from police officers has always been a focus of the code of police ethics.

No one can live alone outside of the society. He grows up, lives among people, communicates with many people of different categories, large and small work groups throughout his life and activity. ³It comes from the need of a person to meet his daily life needs. Living in a community requires to follow the customs, traditions and laws accepted in the society. It is in this process that the set of principles and norms of objectively related, that is, social relations – behavior and manners.

Morality is a set of principles and norms of certain behavior, manners, and behavior that lead and regulate the life and activities of each person based on the coordination of personal and common interests, arising from the objective relationship between a person and society.

According to the order No. 82 of May 30, 2016 of the Minister of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the rules of etiquette of the employees of the internal affairs bodies", a number of qualities and moral characteristics that form professional etiquette are defined in the basic requirements for ethics of the employees of the internal affairs bodies. In particular, if an employee is required to have such qualities as conscientiousness, loyalty, politeness, patience, and honesty, it is indicated that he should be free from vices such as lying, greed, localism, jealousy, favoritism, and selfishness.

¹ Husayn Boiz Koshifiy.(1994) Futuvvatnomayi Sultoniyl/ X.Komilov's translation. Publishing House of People's Heritage named after T.A, Kodiriy, p. 69-70.

²<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ethics>

³ Ismailov B.I. Professional ethics of a lawyer. (2009). Academy of the General Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan, p.188.

The Disciplinary Charter of Internal Affairs bodies was approved by the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan presidential decree No.3413. According to this: "Service discipline in the internal affairs bodies is based on a high level of understanding of each employee and a deep understanding of his duty and personal responsibility for the assigned task."⁴ Chapter 2 of the Disciplinary Charter of internal affairs bodies defined the rules of ethics of employees. According to this: "Code of conduct includes a set of general principles of professional ethics and basic rules of behavior of employees, regardless of the position they hold." Professions adhere to codes of ethics to help them fulfill their duties and ensure high standards of conduct. Police officers face a maze of responsibilities in the performance of their duties. "Code of Ethics of Law Enforcement Agencies" and "Police Code of Conduct" were created in order to clearly indicate the behavior considered appropriate for internal affairs officers and to guide them in the performance of their duties.

People who study the science of morality and practice it know who they are, what is the right thing for the people, and what are they doing on earth. If a person is not aware of himself, he does not know the value of his knowledge, his scholars, good people, good things, and the value of good deeds. A person who knows his fault, confesses it, tries to correct it, and tries to make amends.

Over the years, production, science and technology developed, and social division of labor is developed. The continuation of this process, in turn, led to the emergence of new spheres of activity, each of which performs a specific social function.

According to these moral assessment factors, professional ethics can be divided into several types depending on the role and tasks of each profession in social life: depending on the teaching profession - pedagogic ethics; doctor's ethics depending on medical specialty; depending on the specialty of law enforcement - legal ethics; depending on the specialty of the armed forces - military and officer ethics, etc.

According to philosopher N.E. Muhammadiev (1998), professional ethics appeared and began to function as the responsible of this continuous division of labor, its moral program. In our opinion, the actions and behavior of each person depend on the type and methods of work. Also, professional ethics is necessary to reveal, support and strengthen certain basic human values. These values are kindness, care and compassion, trust and reliability, truthfulness and honesty, justice and fairness, doing duty for the benefit of others, non-violence and non-injury, responsibility and social responsibility.

Employees of internal affairs bodies perform a number of tasks such as "... within their rights, to ensure the rights and legitimate interests of citizens, public order, public safety protection and the fight against crime...", that is, they work in the society as an honorable and extremely responsible human rights defender.

In conclusion, it is appeared that internal affairs officers must be better prepared and more knowledgeable than any other professions. That is the first aspect of the police officers that can be broken if not adhere to codes of conduct. It is an obligation for police officers to uphold the law and policies written in the Disciplinary Charter of Internal Affairs bodies. Thus, professional ethics is a set of actions such as specific professional duty, honor and

⁴ Decree No. 3413 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of November 29, 2017 "On measures to fundamentally improve the procedure for working with personnel of internal affairs bodies and organizing their service"/ National database of legal documents, 30.11.2017., 07/17/3413/0334

dignity that is necessary for the establishment of law and justice in society. It is also necessary to strengthen police officers' dignity, honesty and purity in their professions.

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